

A Modified Wheatstone Bridge for High-Precision Characterization of Resistor Nonlinearity

Vojtěch Janásek¹, Rado Lapuh², Luis Palafox³, *Senior Member, IEEE*, Nikolai Beev⁴, *Member, IEEE*, and Boštjan Voljč⁵

Abstract—The accurate measurement of resistor nonlinearity is crucial in the design of high-precision analog circuits and instrumentation systems. This article presents a modified Wheatstone bridge topology designed to simplify the balancing and improve harmonic sensitivity and measurement accuracy. We introduce a polynomial model to represent the voltage-dependent behavior of the resistor under test. A mathematical framework has been developed for the modified bridge, which links the bridge output directly to the nonlinearity coefficients of the resistor under test. A prototype system was constructed, and measurements were performed on various resistor types (e.g., metal foil and thin film). The experimental results validate the proposed model with high accuracy. Furthermore, an uncertainty analysis is presented, providing a complete characterization of the measurement system performance. The proposed technique offers a robust, sensitive, and simplified method for measuring resistor nonlinearity down to -170 dBc with a single grounded source and no special guarding techniques.

Index Terms—Harmonic distortion, measurement uncertainty, polynomial model, precision measurements, resistor nonlinearity, Wheatstone bridge.

I. INTRODUCTION

RESISTOR linearity is a fundamental assumption in the design of many electronic systems. However, all practical resistors exhibit some degree of nonlinearity [1], where their resistance value changes with applied voltage or current. This effect, while often negligible, can become an important source of error and distortion in high-resolution data converters, precision amplifiers, and measurement instrumentation [2]. In particular, for ultralinear integrating analog-to-digital converters, the voltage dependence of the input resistor modulates the integrator current, creating uncorrectable integral

Received 2 March 2026; revised 4 May 2026; accepted 15 May 2026. Date of publication 3 June 2026; date of current version 17 June 2026. This work was supported in part by the Project 22RPT02 True8DIGIT through European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Program and by the Participating States; and in part by U.K. Participant in Horizon Europe Project 22RPT02 True8DIGIT funded by U.K. Research and Innovation (UKRI) (Signal Conversion Ltd.) under Grant 10,084,012. The Associate Editor coordinating the review process was Dr. Andrea Sossa. (*Corresponding author: Boštjan Voljč.*)

Vojtěch Janásek is with JanasCard, 186 00 Prague, Czech Republic (e-mail: info@janascard.cz).

Rado Lapuh is with Left Right s.p., 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia.

Luis Palafox is with the Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, 38116 Braunschweig, Germany.

Nikolai Beev is with European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN), CH-1211 Geneva, Switzerland, and also with Slovak University of Technology, 812 43 Bratislava, Slovakia.

Boštjan Voljč is with Slovenian Institute of Quality and Metrology, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia (e-mail: bostjan.voljce@siq.si).

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/TIM.2026.3699715

Fig. 1. Wheatstone bridge configuration to measure the nonlinearity of R_x . The voltage sources V_+ and V_- must be synchronized and carefully adjusted for the required amplitude ratio and phase difference.

nonlinearity [3]. Whereas the static resistor temperature dependence is well known [4], at low frequencies, the resistance nonlinearity can also be attributed to the resistive element temperature, which may vary with time as a function of current through the resistor and the resulting Joule heating [5]. Other deviations from ideal resistor behavior include low-frequency excess noise [6], [7] and voltage dependence of the resistance [8]. All of the above-mentioned effects must be considered when selecting components and predicting their impact on precision electronic circuits [9].

Multiple studies in the past have also established the link between harmonic distortion and resistor quality in terms of technology, fabrication defects [10], [11], or state of degradation [12]. Thus, sensitive measurements of harmonic distortion can be used as a performance indicator or reliability predictor. The main advantages over excess noise measurements are in the shorter measurement times and the lack of sensitivity to quasi-DC effects such as temperature- and humidity-induced drift, as well as to thermal electromotive forces.

Direct measurement of resistor nonlinearity is practically infeasible, since the harmonic distortion of high-stability resistors typically falls well below -150 dBc. Characterizing such low levels would require a distortion analyser with a measurement floor better than -160 dBc, which exceeds the capabilities of any currently available instrument.

Consequently, several methods have been proposed to measure this parameter indirectly. A common and highly sensitive technique utilizes a Wheatstone bridge configuration [13], as shown in Fig. 1. This bridge topology is in principle equivalent to modern digital bridges [14], although it is not coaxial. The resistor under test (R_x) is compared against stable reference resistors R_u and R_d . The nonlinearity is inferred from the bridge imbalance as the excitation voltage is varied. Although effective, this approach can suffer from limitations, involving a complex multistep balancing procedure for bridge

Fig. 2. Proposed Wheatstone bridge configuration to measure the nonlinearity of R_x with an operational amplifier maintaining the upper arm voltage so that the left midpoint always remains at virtual ground.

components, and both amplitude and phase alignment of two synchronized sources.

This article addresses these limitations by introducing a modified Wheatstone bridge topology [15] and extends the work focused on measuring capacitor nonlinearity [16] to resistors by providing detailed theory, results for a set of technologies, and uncertainty analysis. The primary contributions of this work are threefold: first, we propose a bridge design that simplifies the measurement procedure, requiring only a single ground-referenced input voltage, as shown in Fig. 2. Second, we formalize a polynomial model for resistor nonlinearity and derive the complete mathematical framework for our proposed bridge. Third, we present a comprehensive experimental validation of the method using various resistor types and provide a rigorous uncertainty analysis for the obtained results.

This article is organized as follows. Section II details the theoretical framework, including the resistor nonlinearity model and the derivation of the governing equations for the modified bridge. Section III describes the experimental setup and measurement procedure. In Section IV, we present the experimental results and discuss their implications. Section V provides a detailed uncertainty analysis. Finally, Section VI concludes this article.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This section establishes the mathematical model for resistor voltage nonlinearity and derives the relationship between the model coefficients and the generation of harmonic distortion components at the bridge output, as shown in Fig. 2.

A. Polynomial Model of Resistor Nonlinearity

The deviation of a resistor R from ideal behavior can be modeled as a dependence of its resistance on the applied voltage v . A practical and effective approach consists in using a normalized polynomial model, where the resistance is expressed relative to its nominal, zero-voltage value R_0 [1]

$$R(v) = R_0 (1 + \alpha v + \beta v^2 + \dots). \quad (1)$$

In this model, α is the first-order (linear) voltage coefficient in V^{-1} , and β is the second-order (quadratic) coefficient in V^{-2} . For high-quality resistors, these coefficients are expected to be very small

$$\alpha \ll 1, \quad \beta \ll 1. \quad (2)$$

This work focuses on the effects of these first two nonlinear terms, since they proved to be the dominant contributions to harmonic distortion.

B. Harmonic Generation

For the bridge shown in Fig. 2, consider pure sinusoidal excitation V_{in} , linear resistors R_u and R_d , and $R_x = R_u = R_d$, and an ideal operational amplifier generating no distortion.

The lower node is driven by $V_{in} \sin \omega t$ and the operational amplifier maintains the left midpoint at virtual ground, $V_l(t) = 0$. The nonlinear resistor in the upper right arm is modeled as

$$R_x(v) = R_u (1 + \alpha v_x + \beta v_x^2) \quad (3)$$

where v_x denotes the voltage across R_x .

1) *Linear Operating Point:* Applying Kirchhoff's current law at the left midpoint using ideal resistors gives

$$V_u = -\frac{R_u}{R_d} V_{in} = -r_b V_{in} \quad (4)$$

where r_b is the bridge resistance ratio $r_b \equiv R_u/R_d$. When the bridge is balanced at ω , $v_{r,1}(t) = 0$, the voltage across R_x is

$$v_x = v_{u,1}(t) - v_{r,1}(t) = -r_b V_{in} \sin(\omega t). \quad (5)$$

2) *Nonlinearity Expansion:* The current flowing through R_x is

$$i_x(v_x) = \frac{v_x}{R_u (1 + \alpha v_x + \beta v_x^2)}. \quad (6)$$

Expanding the denominator and discarding second-order nonlinear terms (containing α^2 , β^2 , $\alpha\beta$, and so on.) due to (2)

$$\frac{1}{1 + \alpha v + \beta v^2} \approx 1 - \alpha v - \beta v^2 \quad (7)$$

the small-signal current through R_x becomes

$$i_x(v) \approx \frac{v_x}{R_u} - \frac{\alpha}{R_u} v_x^2 - \frac{\beta}{R_u} v_x^3. \quad (8)$$

This current would generate harmonic components in V_r and therefore also in v_x . These components would also generate second-order terms in i_x harmonics, which could be safely discarded due to (2). Hence, only a sinusoidal excitation assumption is sufficient for further analysis. Substituting $v_x(t) \approx -V_u \sin \omega t$, currents due to α and β through R_x can be expressed as

$$i_{x,\alpha}(t) = -\frac{\alpha}{R_u} V_u^2 \sin^2 \omega t \quad (9)$$

$$i_{x,\beta}(t) = -\frac{\beta}{R_u} V_u^3 \sin^3 \omega t. \quad (10)$$

Using trigonometric identities, the relevant harmonic components are

$$i_{x,2}(t) = \frac{\alpha V_u^2}{2R_u} \cos(2\omega t) \quad (11)$$

$$i_{x,3}(t) = \frac{\beta V_u^3}{4R_u} \sin(3\omega t). \quad (12)$$

3) *Transfer to the Right Midpoint*: At the harmonic frequencies 2ω and 3ω , neither the source V_{in} nor the op-amp contribute with significant components, so both the lower and the upper node act as virtual grounds for the harmonic components. This holds up to 60 kHz, where the op-amp ~ 60 dB open-loop gain guaranteed this assumption is met, which was confirmed through LTSpice simulation. Thus, the right midpoint sees the equivalent resistance

$$R_{eq} = R_d \parallel R_u = \frac{R_d R_u}{R_d + R_u} = \frac{r_b}{1 + r_b} R_d \quad (13)$$

and the right-midpoint node voltage is

$$v_{r,k}(t) = i_{x,k}(t)R_{eq}, \quad k \in \{2, 3\}. \quad (14)$$

Using (4) and (11), (12), the second-harmonic right-midpoint voltage is

$$V_{r,2} = \frac{r_b^2}{2(1 + r_b)} \alpha V_{in}^2 \quad (15)$$

and the third-harmonic term becomes

$$V_{r,3}(t) = \frac{r_b^3}{4(1 + r_b)} \beta V_{in}^3. \quad (16)$$

Since the differential bridge output is

$$V_b(t) = V_r(t) - V_l(t) = V_r(t) \quad (17)$$

these also represent the measurable harmonic components

$$V_{b,2} = V_{r,2}, \quad V_{b,3} = V_{r,3}. \quad (18)$$

Nonlinearity coefficients are therefore obtained from measured bridge output harmonics

$$\alpha = \frac{2(1 + r_b)}{r_b^2} \frac{V_{b,2}}{V_{in}^2} \quad (19)$$

$$\beta = \frac{4(1 + r_b)}{r_b^3} \frac{V_{b,3}}{V_{in}^3}. \quad (20)$$

For a symmetric bridge ($R_u = R_l$, i.e., $r_b = 1$)

$$V_{b,2} = \frac{1}{4} \alpha V_{in}^2, \quad V_{b,3} = \frac{1}{8} \beta V_{in}^3 \quad (21)$$

and

$$\alpha = 4 \frac{V_{b,2}}{V_{in}^2}, \quad \beta = 8 \frac{V_{b,3}}{V_{in}^3}. \quad (22)$$

These relationships were confirmed by simulation using LTSpice over the applicable component values, where the nonlinear resistors were modeled using (1) [17].

C. Linearity Improvement via Resistor Combination

The voltage dependence of the generated harmonics [see (15) and (16)] provides a powerful technique for improvement of the effective linearity of the R_u and R_d resistors. This can be achieved by connecting multiple resistors in series-parallel [18] or series [16] configurations in order to reduce the voltage across each component, thereby suppressing distortion [13].

Consider a target resistance R_0 implemented using m identical resistors in series. The voltage across each resistor is reduced by a factor of m . Since the k th harmonic amplitude scales as V_0^k , the distortion produced by each resistor is significantly reduced. Assume the harmonic amplitude is equal

TABLE I
MINIMUM SECOND AND THIRD-ORDER HARMONIC COMPONENT REDUCTION FOR SERIES OR SERIES-PARALLEL RESISTOR COMBINATIONS

Resistors in Series (m)	Δh_2 (dB)	Δh_3 (dB)
2	-6.0	-12.0
3	-9.5	-19.1
4	-12.0	-24.1
5	-14.0	-28.0

for all resistors. When the harmonic distortion components from each resistor add in phase (worst case scenario), the harmonic distortion of the combination, when subjected to the same voltage as a single resistor, is reduced by a factor

$$\frac{h_{mR,k}}{h_{R,k}} = m^{1-k} \quad (23)$$

where $h_{mR,k}$ is the k th harmonic level of the m -resistor combination. The same reduction factor applies to a series-parallel network of m^2 resistors. If the harmonic phases are not perfectly aligned, the suppression of harmonics will be even greater. This technique is particularly effective in reduction of higher order harmonics, as shown in Table I.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND PROCEDURE

In order to validate the theoretical framework, a high-precision measurement system based on the modified bridge topology was designed and constructed. This section details the components under test, the hardware implementation, and the measurement protocol.

A. Resistors Under Test

To demonstrate the versatility and performance of the measurement system, a variety of resistor technologies with a nominal value of 10 k Ω were characterized. The selection included.

- 1) Vishay metal foil naked (VAR).
- 2) Vishay metal foil hermetic (VHP).
- 3) Vishay bulk metal foil network (BFN).
- 4) Metal film through-hole (MF).
- 5) Carbon film through-hole (CF).

B. System Implementation

Fig. 3 shows the modified resistance bridge, realized on a custom-designed printed circuit board to minimize stray impedances and ensure repeatable connections.

Fig. 4 shows a block diagram of the complete measurement setup. The key components of the setup are.

- 1) *Reference Resistor R_u* : To ensure that the nonlinearity of the reference arm was significantly lower than that of the R_x , a composite resistor was constructed from a series-parallel network of four 10 k Ω VAR resistors, reducing its effective nonlinearity as described in Section II.
- 2) *Lower Arm Resistors R_l* : The two lower arms of the bridge were populated from a single batch of four high-stability 2 k Ω MF resistors and an additional 1, 8 k Ω

Fig. 3. Photograph of the implemented resistance measurement bridge with coaxial connections to the source (left) and analyser (right), and wire connections to the power supply (left) and measurement of V_u (top). The lower half of the PCB was intended for a pure sine oscillator (not implemented here).

Fig. 4. Block diagram of the complete measurement system, including the modified bridge and the signal generator/analyser. The upper bridge arms are a nominal 10 k Ω , the lower bridge arms are 9.8 k Ω , $C_c = 2.2$ pF, $C_t = (1.5, \dots, 3)$ pF, $R_t = 100$ Ω .

resistor of the same type for each R_d , connected in series. This configuration ensures that the voltage across each resistor is significantly reduced and that any residual nonlinearities are well-matched between the arms, minimizing their differential impact on the measurement.

- 3) *Feedback Amplifier*: A fast, low-distortion OPA1655 operational amplifier generates the excitation voltage V_u for the upper arm of the bridge. The primary advantage of this active feedback topology is that it enables the use of a single, ground-referenced signal source for V_{in} instead of two phase-coupled sources U_+ and U_- (see Fig. 1). The amplifier feedback action also maintains the midpoint of the left bridge arm at a virtual ground potential, minimizing common-mode signals at the differential amplifier input [19]. The contribution of the feedback

amplifier to distortion remains well below -110 dBc over the frequency range used.

- 4) *Balancing Network*: The bridge includes a multiturn trimming potentiometer (R_t) and a variable capacitor (C_t) to null both the real and reactive components of the bridge imbalance, achieving strong rejection of the input signal at the bridge output. This fine adjustment for the sake of balancing the bridge extends the balance to all harmonics present in the excitation signal. We confirmed experimentally in Section IV-B that most commercial signal generators, with harmonics below -80 dBc, are well suited to investigate resistor nonlinearity using this bridge.
- 5) *Differential Amplifier*: The differential voltage at the bridge output is amplified by a factor of 500 using a custom instrumentation amplifier implemented on the printed circuit board. This amplifier is constructed using low-distortion OPA1656 operational amplifiers and 0.1 % tolerance MF resistors in order to achieve a high common-mode rejection ratio in excess of 100 dB. Because the feedback amplifier minimizes the common-mode voltage at the bridge output, the contribution of the differential amplifier to distortion remains well below -110 dBc over the used frequency range.
- 6) *Source and Analyser*: An audio precision APx555 audio analyser was used for both signal generation and analysis. Its generator provided the sinusoidal excitation signal (V_{in}) with harmonic distortion below -120 dBc. The analyser section of the instrument features similarly low intrinsic distortion. The use of long data records (up to 1.2×10^6 samples) and signal averaging allowed the low-level harmonic signals to be effectively distinguished from noise.

C. Measurement Procedure

For each resistor, harmonic distortion was measured by following a procedure.

- 1) The resistor was soldered at the designated R_x position on the bridge PCB to ensure a stable, low-resistance connection.
- 2) The APx555 generator output was connected to the bridge input (V_{in}), and the amplified bridge output (V_{out}) was connected to the analyser input.
- 3) The generator was configured to produce a sinusoidal signal at a specified frequency and amplitude (e.g., 10 kHz at 7.07 V rms).
- 4) The bridge was carefully balanced using the trimming potentiometer R_t and the variable capacitor C_t to minimize the amplitude of the fundamental frequency component at the output of the differential amplifier. The balance was monitored using the FFT display of the analyser. Typically, V_{out} fundamental component amplitude achieved was between -65 dBV (0.13 μ V) -35 dBV (4 μ V), corresponding to the lowest and to the highest frequency, respectively.
- 5) Once the minimum was found, the analyser was configured to acquire and average the output signal spectrum.

The amplitudes of the fundamental, second and third-harmonic components were recorded from the FFT. Harmonic amplitudes in V_{out} were measured from -51 dBV at the highest distortion down to -128 dBV at the lowest distortion, the latter being close to the noise floor.

- 6) The measurement was repeated across a range of excitation voltages and frequencies to characterize the scaling of the harmonic components and their frequency dependence.

The first measurement was performed on a VAR resistor, where four of the same resistors were used for R_u . This arrangement reduces the maximum harmonic distortion from R_u by 6 dB at the second harmonic and 12 dB for the third. (see Table I), assuming the same harmonic distortion amplitude across the resistor type. This defined the detection limit, being equal to the harmonic distortion voltage generated by R_u . The rest of the resistors were measured using the same procedure. The final harmonic distortion values in dBc were subsequently calculated relative to V_{in} , by correcting the measured spectral amplitudes for the whole bridge transfer function gain.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the experimental results obtained with the modified bridge. First, we validate the resistor nonlinearity model presented in Section II. Next, we show that the bridge rejection is equally effective for the fundamental tone of the excitation signal and its harmonics. Finally, we present the measured nonlinearity for various resistor technologies and discuss the implications of the findings.

While the nonlinearity of a resistor can be fully described using model coefficients α and β , it is often useful to report a more intuitive and application-oriented figure of merit: the effective harmonic distortion at a given sinusoidal excitation voltage. This approach matches the harmonic distortion measured via bridge circuits or spectral analysis of the current and can be derived directly from α and β in the model and from the excitation amplitude. Taking the differential amplifier gain G_{DA} into account, we define h_2 and h_3 as a resistor distortion reported in this section from (11), (12) using (26), (27)

$$h_2 = \left| \frac{I_{2\omega}}{I_\omega} \right| = \frac{\alpha V_x}{2} = \frac{1 + r_b}{r_b} \frac{V_{\text{out},2}}{V_{\text{in}} G_{\text{DA}}} \quad (24)$$

$$h_3 = \left| \frac{I_{3\omega}}{I_\omega} \right| = \frac{\beta V_x^2}{4} = \frac{1 + r_b}{r_b} \frac{V_{\text{out},3}}{V_{\text{in}} G_{\text{DA}}}. \quad (25)$$

Hence, distortion values must always be reported with the corresponding voltage applied across R_x .

A. Experimental Validation of the Nonlinearity Model

A key prediction of the theoretical model (15), (16) is that for weak nonlinearities, the amplitude of the second harmonic component should scale quadratically with the excitation voltage (V_{in}^2), while the third harmonic should scale cubically (V_{in}^3). To verify this, a high-stability 10 k Ω BFN resistor

Fig. 5. Measured second and third-harmonic amplitudes of a 10 k Ω BFN resistor as a function of input voltage. The lines show the excellent agreement with the theoretical model predicted quadratic (V_u^2) and cubic (V_u^3) scaling.

was measured at a fundamental frequency of 10 kHz while changing V_{in} to set rms V_u from 3 to 7 V.

Fig. 5 plots the measured amplitudes of the second and third-harmonic components as a function of V_u , applied across R_x . The solid lines represent the theoretical quadratic and cubic scaling laws. The experimental data show excellent agreement with the model predictions. This result strongly supports the validity of the polynomial model and confirms that the dominant contributions to the second and third harmonics arise from the α and β coefficients, respectively.

B. Rejection of Excitation Signal Harmonics

A key advantage of the bridge is its ability to reject harmonic content from the excitation source (V_{in}) in the same way it rejects the fundamental. To quantify this crucial feature for the proposed active bridge, an experiment was conducted in order to assess the sensitivity of the system to input signal purity.

A baseline measurement using an MF resistor as R_x was first established using a clean input signal (total harmonic distortion ≤ -120 dBc), yielding the intrinsic distortion of the resistor. The bridge was balanced to suppress the fundamental component at the output $V_{\text{out},1}$ to approximately -50 dBV.

The measurement was then repeated, but with controlled levels of second and third-harmonic distortion (from -80 dBc down to -20 dBc) intentionally introduced into the V_{in} signal.

Fig. 6 shows the final calculated harmonic distortion of the resistor as a function of the input injected distortion. When the input harmonics are strong, they leak through the imperfectly balanced bridge and dominate the measurement, resulting in an artificially high calculated resistor distortion. As the injected distortion is attenuated (e.g. from -20 to -50 dBc), the calculated resistor distortion drops by a corresponding 10 dB.

Significantly, this 1:1 trend stops once the input distortion is below -70 dBc. The calculated harmonic levels then converge to a stable floor of -150 dBc for h_2 and -162 dBc for h_3 . This floor is the intrinsic nonlinearity of the measured resistor, which matches the baseline measurement taken with the clean signal.

This experiment confirms that the active balancing mechanism is effective against source harmonics. It demonstrates that for a typical bridge balance, an input signal with harmonic distortion around or below -80 dBc is sufficiently pure, since

Fig. 6. Calculated second and third-harmonic distortion of the measured MF resistor as a function of the harmonic distortion level injected into the input signal V_{in} . The data were taken on a 10 k Ω MF resistor at 7.071 V and 7 kHz. The plots demonstrate that the measurement converges to the true intrinsic distortion of the resistor (the floor) once the harmonic content of the input signal is suppressed below -80 dBc, for the bridge balanced at $V_{out,1} = -50$ dBV.

its contribution is attenuated below the intrinsic distortion of the reference resistor R_u . It also demonstrates that the bridge balance effectively rejects the signal harmonics generated by the signal source (V_{in}) and by the operational amplifier (V_u).

C. Calculation of Nonlinearity Coefficients

Following the model (3), the primary goal of the measurement is to determine the nonlinearity coefficients α and β from the measured harmonic distortion levels. Based on the relationships derived in (24) and (25), the coefficients can be calculated directly from the harmonic distortion expressed in decibels relative to the carrier (dBc).

Let h_2 and h_3 be the measured second and third-harmonic distortion levels in dBc, and V_x be the peak excitation voltage across the measured resistor. The coefficients are given by

$$\alpha = \frac{2}{V_x} \cdot 10^{h_2/20} \quad (26)$$

$$\beta = \frac{4}{V_x^2} \cdot 10^{h_3/20}. \quad (27)$$

D. Nonlinearity of Different Resistor Technologies

Using the described measurement system, the nonlinearity of several common 10-k Ω resistor types was characterized over a frequency range of 5 Hz to 20 kHz with 7 V rms applied across them. Figs. 7 and 8 plot the measured second and third-harmonic distortion, respectively.

While Figs. 7 and 8 show the mean measured values, plotting the associated uncertainties for every data point would render the graphs unreadable. Furthermore, as discussed in the uncertainty analysis, the relative uncertainty increases significantly for measurements at very low distortion levels, causing the raw measurement trace as a function of frequency to appear nonsmooth.

To provide a clearer and more practical representation of component performance, two additional figures (Figs. 9 and 10) are presented. These plots show the distortion upper bound, calculated by arithmetically adding the combined uncertainty ($k = 1$) to the measured harmonic amplitude. This

Fig. 7. Measured second harmonic distortion (h_2) for various 10-k Ω resistor technologies as a function of frequency. The marker and line styles defined here are consistent across Figs. 8–10.

Fig. 8. Measured third-harmonic distortion (h_3) for various 10-k Ω resistor technologies as a function of frequency.

Fig. 9. Upper bound of second harmonic distortion (h_2) for selected resistors. The lines represent the measured harmonic amplitudes (from Fig. 7) with their combined uncertainty added.

representation serves as a more robust “worst case” specification for each resistor type, which is often the primary interest for circuit designers selecting high-performance components.

A summary of the nonlinearity coefficients, calculated at 7.071 V and 10 kHz, is provided in Table II.

E. Discussion

The results reveal several important characteristics of resistor nonlinearity.

Fig. 10. Upper bound of third-harmonic distortion (h_3) for selected resistors. The lines represent the measured harmonic amplitudes (from Fig. 8) with their combined uncertainty added.

TABLE II
SUMMARY OF NONLINEARITY COEFFICIENTS AT 1 KHz
WITH $k = 1$ UNCERTAINTIES

Resistor Type	α (V^{-1})	β (V^{-2})
VAR	$4.6(28) \times 10^{-10}$	$2.4(6) \times 10^{-10}$
VHP	$7.7(28) \times 10^{-10}$	$8.1(6) \times 10^{-10}$
BFN	$6.8(28) \times 10^{-10}$	$2.33(5) \times 10^{-8}$
MF	$7.6(28) \times 10^{-9}$	$2.0(6) \times 10^{-10}$
CF	$5.5(3) \times 10^{-9}$	$3.04(9) \times 10^{-9}$

- 1) *Second-Order Nonlinearity (α)*: As shown in Fig. 7, the second harmonic distortion for all resistor types tested is extremely low, generally around or below -150 dBc up to 5 kHz. This indicates that the first-order voltage coefficient α is very small for modern precision and general-purpose resistors. An increase is observed above 5 kHz, and this trend is common for all tested resistors.
- 2) *Third-Order Nonlinearity (β)*: The third-harmonic distortion, shown in Fig. 8, exhibits more significant variation between technologies, particularly at low frequencies. VAR, VHP, and MF resistors demonstrate the best performance, with consistently low distortion across the entire frequency range. On the contrary, the BFN and the CF resistor show significantly elevated third-harmonic distortion at frequencies below 1 kHz. This low-frequency behavior can likely be attributed to electrothermal effects. At lower frequencies, the resistor element has sufficient time to experience temperature variations within a single cycle of the excitation current (Joule heating). This temperature fluctuation, in turn, modulates the resistance via its temperature coefficient, creating a strong third-harmonic component. The thermal time constant of the resistor physical package and the material properties dictate the frequency at which this effect rolls off. This phenomenon is more pronounced in compact packages such as the chip network, or in materials with higher thermal sensitivity.

These findings underscore the importance of careful component selection in high-precision analog circuits. For applications requiring the highest linearity, particularly at

audio and subaudio frequencies, VAR, VHP, and certain MF resistors are the superior choices.

V. UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS

A comprehensive uncertainty analysis was performed in accordance with the guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement (GUM) [20]. This section outlines the uncertainty model, the evaluation of individual uncertainty components, and the calculation of the combined uncertainty for the nonlinearity coefficients and harmonic distortions reported in this article.

A. Uncertainty Model

The nonlinearity coefficients α and β are not measured directly but are calculated from several input quantities. Based on (19) and (20) and taking the differential amplifier gain G_{DA} into account, the model equations relating the coefficients to the measured quantities are

$$\alpha = \frac{2(1 + r_b)}{r_b^2} \frac{V_{out,2}}{G_{DA,2} V_{in}^2} \quad (28)$$

$$\beta = \frac{4(1 + r_b)}{r_b^3} \frac{V_{out,3}}{G_{DA,3} V_{in}^3} \quad (29)$$

where V_{in} is the peak excitation voltage, $V_{out,k}$ is the peak voltage of the k th harmonic at the output of the differential amplifier, and $G_{DA,k}$ is the frequency-dependent gain of the differential amplifier at the k th harmonic frequency.

Using the resistor distortion defined in (24) and (25), it follows that the relative uncertainty in α and β is equal to the relative uncertainty in h_2 and h_3 , respectively.

B. Evaluation of Uncertainty Components

The uncertainty of each input quantity in (28) and (29) was evaluated as follows.

- 1) *Input Voltage ($u(V_{in})$)*: The voltage V_{in} was set and monitored during the measurement using an AC voltmeter. Its uncertainty is dominated by the source stability and is estimated to be within 0.5 %.
- 2) *Amplifier Gain ($u(G_{DA,k})$)*: The gain of the differential amplifier is determined by the tolerances of its gain-defining resistors to 0.1 %. Based on LTSpice simulations and gain measurements, the gain flatness was evaluated to stay within 1 % over the whole used frequency band.
- 3) *Bridge Resistance Ratio ($u(r_b)$)*: This ratio defines the voltage across the R_x . It was determined by measuring the voltage ratio V_u/V_{in} using an AC voltmeter ratio, reaching an estimated uncertainty of 0.2 %.
- 4) *Output Harmonic Voltage ($u(V_{out,k})$)*: This is the most complex component, as it covers deviations neglected in Section II, impacting the measured harmonic amplitude by the spectrum analyser $V_{SA,k}$. Furthermore, this measurement must be corrected for reference resistor harmonic cancellation and the noise bias. Its uncertainty is a combination of random (Type A) and systematic (Type B) effects.

C. Uncertainty of Measured Harmonics

The measured distortion components $V_{\text{out},k}$ due to R_x are calculated from the measured spectral amplitudes at the bridge output $V_{\text{SA},k}$ using the model

$$V_{\text{out},k} = V_{\text{SA},k} + \delta_{V_{\text{in}},k} + \delta_{D_{\text{A}},k} + \delta_{S_{\text{A}},k} + \delta_{R_{\text{u}},k} + \delta_{R_{\text{d}},k} \quad (30)$$

where all δ addends correspond to contributions not originating from R_x and the uncertainty of $V_{\text{out},k}$ is then calculated as

$$u(V_{\text{out},k}) = \sqrt{u(V_{\text{SA},k})^2 + \sum \delta_{\text{comp},k}^2} \quad (31)$$

where $u(V_{\text{SA},k})$ is type A uncertainty, primarily due to system noise appearing in the SA sampled record and it increases towards the obtained spectrum noise floor. Harmonic contributions to the output voltage harmonics (δ) propagate from their source to the output, where they combine with the measured harmonics originating from the R_x . Their propagation depends on the location in the bridge circuit where they are generated. The final value for $V_{\text{out},k}$ is determined after applying two significant corrections to the raw spectral data $V_{\text{SA},k}$. The key parameter for these harmonic contributions is the bridge balance, achieving the ratio of $V_{\text{b},k}/V_{\text{b},1} < -70$ dB, $k \in \{2, 3\}$.

- 1) *Input Voltage Harmonics* ($\delta_{V_{\text{in}},k}$): Source voltage harmonic distortions are bounded to -120 dBc by the source used. The source voltage is scaled and mirrored to V_{u} using the OPA1655 operational amplifier, which is also specified for harmonic distortion below -120 dBc in the frequency range used. With the bridge being balanced, the combined source and operational amplifier harmonics are also reduced by the same amount in V_{b} . Using a conservative -100 and -110 dB as harmonic contributions to the second and third harmonic, respectively, the bridge nulling reduces $\delta_{V_{\text{in}},k}$ well below the harmonic amplitudes measured. Since the phase of these residual harmonics is not known, the uncertainty distribution is U-shaped.
- 2) *Differential Amplifier Harmonics* ($\delta_{D_{\text{A}},k}$): The differential amplifier is built using an instrumentation amplifier topology around low-distortion OPA1656 operational amplifiers and 0.1 % gain-defining resistors. It was characterized for its common-mode rejection ratio to be below -100 dB and harmonic distortions to be below -110 dB over the used frequency range. Harmonics are generated from $V_{\text{b},1}$, and this harmonic distortion ratio was used as a contribution to $\delta_{D_{\text{A}},k}$. This uncertainty distribution is U-shaped.
- 3) *Spectrum Analyser Harmonic Correction* ($\delta_{S_{\text{A}},k}$): The spectrum analyser measures harmonics in V_{b} , which can be found close to the noise floor, despite using the longest record available (1.2×10^6 samples) to reduce the FFT noise floor. When measuring a tone with an amplitude close to the noise floor, the magnitude estimate from an FFT exhibits a positive bias [21]. This occurs because the magnitude is calculated from noisy in-phase and quadrature components, a process described by the Rice distribution. In order to obtain an

unbiased estimate of the true harmonic amplitude, $V_{\text{corr},k}$, the following correction is applied:

$$V_{\text{corr},k} = \sqrt{(V'_{\text{SA},k})^2 - NF^2} \quad (32)$$

where NF is the rms noise level in a single FFT bin, determined from adjacent noise only bins. This correction is only applied when the measured noise floor is sufficiently high ($NF > 6$ dB) to be reliable. The $NF + 6$ dB therefore defines the noise floor limit for the harmonics measurement. The uncertainty of this corrected value is estimated based on the noise level and the number of averages used in the measurement, and the spectrum analyser level measurement uncertainty. It turns out to be the dominant contribution for low measured harmonic values. Measured harmonics seen by the spectrum analyser were always higher than -77 dB from the fundamental tone, remaining from the bridge balance. Most commercial spectrum analysers with harmonics below -80 dBc are therefore well suited to investigate resistor nonlinearity using this bridge.

- 4) *Reference Resistor Harmonic Correction* ($\delta_{R_{\text{u}},k}$): Since the reference resistor R_{u} is a 2×2 series-parallel network ($m = 2$), it also generates harmonic distortion. Assuming the distortion mechanisms are identical, the harmonics from R_{u} are expected to be in-phase with those from the R_x for the first measurement, causing a partial cancellation at the bridge output. The measured voltage $V_{\text{SA},k}$ is therefore an underestimate of the true harmonic voltage generated by the R_x alone. The corrected harmonic voltage, $V_{\text{SAcorr},k}$, is calculated by dividing the measured value by the cancellation factor

$$V_{\text{SAcorr},k} = \frac{V_{\text{SA},k}}{1 - m^{-(k-1)}}. \quad (33)$$

For our configuration with $m = 2$ and using the same resistors for R_{u} and R_x , the measured second harmonic is increased by a factor of 2 (+6.0dB) and the third harmonic by a factor of 4/3 (+2.5dB). The uncertainty of this correction is asymmetric. Since the cancellation is maximal for perfect phase alignment, the true value is bounded by $[V_{\text{SAcorr},k} - 2\delta_{R_{\text{u}},k}, V_{\text{SAcorr},k}]$, where $\delta_{R_{\text{u}},k}$ is the magnitude of the harmonic contribution of the reference resistor. This is treated as a one-sided, U-shaped distribution. When measuring other resistors (R_{u} and R_x are not of the same type), the R_{u} distortion clearly sets the detection limit, where its harmonic contribution is equal to the harmonic contribution of the measured resistor.

- 5) *Lower Bridge Arms Harmonics* ($\delta_{R_{\text{d}},k}$): Harmonic contribution from R_{d} is reduced by serial connection of five resistors. By using the same resistor types from the same batch, they likely generate harmonics that are in-phase, causing further cancellation at the bridge output. In our uncertainty calculation, the measured values for the MF resistor were used with an appropriate scaling due to $m = 5$. This uncertainty distribution is U-shaped.

Fig. 11. Bridge positive uncertainty at 1 and 20 kHz for h_2 and h_3 as a function of measured resistor harmonic distortion.

D. Bridge Performance

While uncertainty was calculated for each harmonic measurement, it is informative to present a more general uncertainty capability of the reported bridge, which mainly depends on the measured harmonic level. Fig. 11 shows the calculated uncertainty for the bridge and its components as described in this article at two fundamental frequencies. At 1 kHz, the bridge balance was $V_{SA,1} = -50$ dBV and at 20 kHz, the bridge balance was $V_{SA,1} = -30$ dBV. Figs. 7 and 8 show the noise floor and detection limit achieved. As the uncertainty given in logarithmic units becomes nonsymmetrical, only the positive uncertainty is plotted. While uncertainties for both harmonics at 1 kHz and $u(h_3)$ at 20 kHz are similar, there is a huge deviation observed for $u(h_2)$ at 20 kHz. This is primarily due to the increased h_2 of R_u (increased detection limit).

The uncertainty evaluation demonstrated that the source and spectrum analyser contributions were minimal due to the achieved $V_{b,k}/V_{b,1} < -70$ dB in all cases. This implies that similar results could be achieved using far less demanding instrumentation used for source and spectrum analyser, where their harmonic distortion of -80 dBc would be sufficient, with higher uncertainties approaching the noise limit. However, it is essential to use long FFT records to reduce the FFT noise floor below the measured harmonics. Such a measurement setup was tested using a programmable function generator achieving harmonic distortion < -70 dBc and a 10-bit oscilloscope using 128 kSample memory and 16 spectrum averages. The system captured similar results for CF and MF resistors at frequencies > 1 kHz.

VI. CONCLUSION

This article presents a modified Wheatstone bridge for the simplified and accurate measurement of resistor nonlinearity. By leveraging a polynomial model and a carefully designed bridge topology, we have demonstrated a method that directly yields the nonlinearity coefficients and can measure harmonic distortions below -170 dBc using a single voltage source and a single-channel long-record spectrum analyser. The measurement configuration does not require differential drive, coaxial design, or complex guarding. The mathematical framework was derived, an experimental prototype was built and tested, and complete measurement uncertainty analysis was performed and reported.

The results obtained for various resistor types, from high-stability metal foil to standard carbon composition, validate the model and demonstrate the high sensitivity of the system. A key contribution of this work is the active bridge topology, which simplifies the measurement setup and the measurement procedure, and increases robustness due to the automatic adjustment of the voltage amplitude and phase over the measured resistor. The upper bound harmonic distortions are provided for a selection of resistor technologies aimed at engineers and researchers who require precise knowledge of resistor behavior for demanding applications. Future work will involve the use of a similar solution for the measurement of capacitor distortions.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Horowitz and W. Hill, *The Art Electronics: The X-Chapters*. Cambridge, U.K.: Cambridge Univ. Press, 2020.
- [2] W. G. K. Ihlenfeld and R. T. B. Vasconcellos, "A digital quadrature bridge for impedance measurements," in *Proc. 29th Conf. Precis. Electromagn. Meas. (CPEM)*, Aug. 2014, pp. 106–107.
- [3] W. C. Goetze, "8.5-digit integrating analog-to-digital converter with 16-bit digitizing capability," *Hewlett-Packard J.*, vol. 40, pp. 8–15, Apr. 1989.
- [4] F. Zandman, "Non-linearity of resistance/temperature characteristic: Its influence on performance of precision resistors," VPG Foil Resistors, Chesterbrook, PA, USA, Tehn. Note 108, Feb. 2018.
- [5] B. Hofer, "Designing for ultra-low THD+N (Part 2)," *audioXpress Mag., Practical T&M*, vol. 44, no. 12, pp. 18–23, Nov. 2013.
- [6] F. Seifert, "Resistor current noise measurements," LIGO Scientific Collaboration, Pasadena, CA, USAA, Tech. Rep. LIGO-T0900200-v1, 2009.
- [7] N. Beev, "Measurement of excess noise in thin film and metal foil resistor networks," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Instrum. Meas. Technol. Conf. (I2MTC)*, Ottawa, ON, Canada, May 2022, pp. 1–6.
- [8] T. Williams and J. Thomas, "A comparison of the noise and voltage coefficients of precision metal film and carbon film resistors," *IRE Trans. Compon. Parts*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 58–62, Jun. 1959.
- [9] W. G. K. Ihlenfeld and R. T. B. Vasconcellos, "On the nonlinear voltage dependence of passive electronic components," in *Proc. 29th Conf. Precis. Electromagn. Meas. (CPEM)*, Aug. 2014, pp. 96–97.
- [10] S. Kasukabe and M. Tanaka, "Reliability evaluation of thick film resistors through measurement of third harmonic index," *Act. Passive Electron. Compon.*, vol. 8, nos. 3–4, 1981, Art. no. 506201.
- [11] E. P. Vandamme and L. K. J. Vandamme, "Current crowding and its effect on 1/f noise and third harmonic distortion—A case study for quality assessment of resistors," *Microelectron. Rel.*, vol. 40, no. 11, pp. 1847–1853, Nov. 2000.
- [12] B. K. Jones and Y. Z. Xu, "Characterisation of electromigration damage by multiple electrical measurements," *Microelectron. Rel.*, vol. 33, nos. 11–12, pp. 1829–1840, Sep. 1993.
- [13] S. Groner and S. Wurcer, "Quadrature bridge measures harmonic distortion in capacitors," *Linear Audio*, vol. 12, pp. 165–177, Jan. 2016.
- [14] Y. Wang and S. Schlamminger, "A digital four-arm bridge for the comparison of resistance with capacitance," *Metrologia*, vol. 61, no. 5, Sep. 2024, Art. no. 055009.
- [15] V. Janásek, N. Beev, B. Voljč, and R. Lapuh, "Quadrature bridge for capacitor non-linearity measurement," in *Proc. Conf. Precis. Electromagn. Meas. (CPEM)*, Jul. 2024, pp. 1–2.
- [16] S. Groner, "Letters to the editor: Resistor non-linearity—There's more to Ω than meets the eye," *Linear Audio*, vols. 1–6, pp. 1–9, Apr. 2014.
- [17] M. Engelhardt, *LTspice XVII*, 3rd ed., Wilmington, MA, USA: Analog Devices Corporation, 2016.
- [18] E. Simon, "Resistor non-linearity—There's more to Ω than meets the eye," *Linear Audio*, vol. 1, pp. 138–146, Apr. 2011.
- [19] J. Williams, "Bridge circuits," Linear Technol., Milpitas, MA, USA, Appl. Note AN43, 2011.
- [20] *Evaluation of Measurement Data—Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement*, document JCGM 100:2008, BIPM, IEC, IFCC, ILAC, ISO, IUPAC, IUPAP, and OIML, Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology, Sèvres, France, 2008, doi: [10.59161/JCGM100-2008E](https://doi.org/10.59161/JCGM100-2008E).
- [21] S. O. Rice, "Mathematical analysis of random noise, Part I," *Bell Syst. Tech. J.*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 282–332, 1944.